

**D6.5 Report on the One Health
EJP Continuing Professional
Development Module (Y2)**

WP6: Education and Training

Responsible Partner: UoS (P23)

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Introduction

Outbreaks or events involving new or re-emerging zoonoses can occur anytime and everywhere. The One Health concept recognizes that human health is tightly connected to the health of animals and the environment. Consequently, strengthening the human-veterinary collaboration is essential to prevent, detect and respond to zoonotic threats. Yet, implementation and operationalization of the One Health concept often remains a challenge. In addition, countries differ across Europe (and worldwide) and thus the approaches to One Health issues do also. Sharing best practices and experiences of One Health approaches is thought to be key in strengthening One Health collaboration across Europe.

The major outbreak of Q fever among humans that occurred in 2007 marked a turning point in how the Dutch Government responds to emerging zoonotic diseases. Consequently, a systematic One Health approach was developed and officially implemented for the purpose of sharing, assessing and responding to signals of new and re-emerging zoonotic infections, in which veterinary and medical professionals work together. In 2011, this integrated human-veterinary risk analysis structure was formally adopted by the Dutch Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport and the Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality as the national Zoonoses Structure.

The Dutch National Coordination Centre for Communicable Disease Control within the RIVM answered the One Health EJP call for hosting of the Continuing Professional development Module on outbreak preparedness in 2019. In the event of an outbreak in the Netherlands, the National Coordination Centre for Communicable Disease Control within the RIVM is responsible for prompt and effective response, as well as scientific advice on outbreak control measures to the government and for implementation by health professionals. In collaboration with the centre for Zoonoses and environmental microbiology within the RIVM (responsible for the early warning and risk assessment of the transmission of pathogenic microorganisms from animals, food and the environment to humans in the Netherlands), the National School of Public Health (NSPOH), and the Netherlands Food and Consumer Product Safety Authority (NVWA) a project team was assembled and a CPD module program developed.

Organization of the (physical) workshop in March 2020

Originally, a 2-day face-to-face meeting was planned and organized for 25 delegates and 5 speakers to take place on March 12 & 13th, 2020, at the NH hotel in Utrecht, The Netherlands (see also "Save the Date" Promotional Flyer in annex 1). After the delegate selection process, hotel rooms, meeting location, catering and a social dinner event were pre-booked by the project team, as well as merchandise ordered by the OHEJP Comms

Team. Unfortunately, on March 9th, 2020, the project team was forced to postpone the CPD module until further notice, due to the recent COVID-19 outbreak across Europe. Over half the delegates chose not to travel or could not travel due to their countries travel restrictions e.g. Italy. In addition, one was concerned that of those delegates who had not officially cancelled, some of these may still be no-shows.

Organization of the (virtual) workshop in November 2020

After postponing the CPD module in March 2020 (due to COVID-19), alternative options to still deliver the event in 2020 were discussed with the WP6 and Comms team. The details of these discussions included the current workload and availability of the project team due to their involvement in the COVID-response, the uncertainty of future travel restrictions, the prolonged waiting time for delegates who had successfully registered, delegates having lost their money due to travel cancellations, and the fact that the event was delayed once before (from December 2019 to April 2020). In the end, it was agreed to re-structure the original programme to fit a virtual event, consisting of a mixture of online lectures and interactive breakout sessions in working groups, and re-arrange experts in the project team to fit availability for the upcoming event.

Lastly, the (online) CPD module on outbreak preparedness successfully took place on November 16th & 17th, 2020 (see also Full Promotional Flyer in annex 2). Although, a physical meeting would have offered a lot more flexibility and interactive options, the participating 16 delegates reacted very positive to the provided alternative. Below screenshot depicts the results of the short evaluation at the end of the module.

Theme and Overview

Sharing best practices and experiences of One Health approaches stands at the center of this module, providing a learning platform aimed at knowledge integration and strengthening of One Health collaboration across Europe.

The (online) CPD module on outbreak preparedness consisted of three sessions: (1) the basic principles of infectious disease control, (2) the zoonoses response structure – example of the Netherlands and lessons learned from past outbreaks, and (3) risk perception and communication to professionals and the public. Unfortunately, the originally planned simulation game could not be re-structured into an online activity. Hence, the duration of the event was shortened to 1,5 days. All three sessions contained a mixture of online lectures and interactive breakout sessions in working groups. Participants learned several technical skills that they were able to practice on case studies. An overview of the event programme is provided in Annex 3.

During the first session, delegates followed a presentation to obtain insight into the basic principles of infectious disease control. Besides the different steps in outbreak investigation and their importance, past outbreaks in the Netherlands were used as examples to make the lecture more vivid. Next, delegates were divided into four groups, provided with a scenario, and asked to assess the given signal based on the outbreak investigation processes presented in the lecture. Afterwards, every group was asked to present their scenario and findings to the plenary group, followed by a plenary discussion.

The second session started with a lecture on the Dutch zoonoses structure, an integrated human-veterinary risk analysis structure for efficient signalling, risk-assessment and control of emerging zoonoses. Besides lessons learned from past outbreaks, this lecture also included the most recent insights of COVID-19 in animals. After the lecture, delegates were divided into two groups, assigned different stakeholder roles and information. During the following role-play delegates were led to simulate a Signalling Forum Zoonoses and discuss possible zoonotic threats and their potential risks to public health. Afterwards, a plenary discussion took place.

The third session focused on risk perception and communication, including the different perspectives of risks, information needs, as well as goals, challenges and barriers in communication to professionals and the public. Next, delegates were divided into four groups to discuss the pro's and con's of a zoonotic communication message, which they were asked to select prior to the session. Afterwards, every group was asked to present their selected communication message and share their findings with the plenary group, followed by a plenary discussion.

At the end of the 1,5-day CPD module on outbreak preparedness, a plenary wrap-up took place, including a short evaluation of the module via Mentimeter.

Aims and Objectives

Sharing best practices and experiences of One Health approaches stands at the centre of this module, providing a learning platform aimed at knowledge integration and strengthening of One Health collaboration across Europe.

This outbreak preparedness module aimed to provide:

- an understanding of the basic principles of infectious disease control, as well as monitoring and evaluation;
- a platform to share experiences and lessons learned from past outbreaks;
- an understanding of the Dutch zoonoses response structure, as an example of a One Health approach in prevention and response;
- insight into relevant aspects of risk perception and communication to professionals and the public;
- an interactive learning on risk assessment and response to a zoonotic disease.

Experts & Speakers

The team we established to work on this CPD module is thought to be a strong mix of professionals who each bring a wealth of expertise and competences to this module. They not only provide scientific expertise, but are also professionals who have worked in the field, and now convert their knowledge and experience into policy advice:

Dr. Corien Swaan is head of the department for Prevention & Control at the National Coordination Centre for Communicable Disease Control within the RIVM. After working with Médecins sans Frontières in mainly Asian countries until 2000, she completed her specialization at the public health services in Leiden, the Netherlands. In 2006 she started working at the RIVM, involved in coordination of infectious disease control and IHR implementation, including preparedness and response for zoonotic diseases. In 2012 she became head of the department. In 2017, the department was assigned WHO Collaborative Centre for Preparedness and IHR Monitoring & Evaluation and last year it started as WP leader for trainings in the Joint Action 'Healthy Gateways'. She successfully defended her thesis Timeliness of infectious disease notification & response systems in December 2019. Currently she is involved in the COVID-19 response in the Netherlands.

Dr. Hans van den Kerkhof is a Public Health physician specialised in control of communicable diseases. After finishing his general medical training in 1982 he trained for 2 years in preparation for working in a hospital setting in Africa. From 1984-1990 he was employed in a rural hospital in Ghana where he both did clinical work and acted as a district

medical officer being responsible for vaccination and other public health related programs. After his return he worked as a public health physician specialized in control of infectious diseases in a regional public health service in the Netherlands and in 2006 he joined the newly established national Center for Control of infectious diseases at the RIVM in Bilthoven as a coordinator responsible for the relations between the national center and the 25 regional public health services. Besides these activities he is also involved in the second line advice for control of outbreaks at national level and he has always been active in teaching. Cooperation of the medical and the veterinary sector in control of zoonoses has always had his strong interest. Since 2010 he coordinates the support of the Dutch overseas territories in the Caribbean related to the International Health Regulations and has been visiting the area regularly.

Dr. Kitty Maassen is head of the department Animal & Vector at the Center of Zoonoses and Environmental microbiology within the RIVM. The focus of this department is to study public health related to zoonotic agents via wild life and livestock, including antibiotic resistance and via vectors, such as ticks and mosquitos. She is working at the RIVM since 2011. Prior to this post, she was also working in the area of zoonoses at the Central Veterinary Institute in Lelystad (currently WBVR). One of her current tasks is coordinating the signaling forum as part of the Dutch integrated risk analysis structure for zoonoses in which (potential) zoonotic signals are discussed and assessed in a monthly meeting with representatives from the human health, veterinary health and food safety sectors. In line with this work she is coordinator of the project COHESIVE of the One Health European Joint Programme.

Drs. Ingrid Keur received her degree as a veterinarian from Ghent University in 2011 and a masters' degree in One Health from the University of Edinburgh in 2017. After working as a veterinary surgeon at an animal shelter in New Delhi, she worked as an inspector at the Border Inspection Post on Amsterdam's Schiphol Airport and in Rotterdam's harbor, and as liaison officer for the National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) at the Centre for Zoonosis and Environmental Biology. She currently works as a senior inspector at the incident and crisis centre of the Netherlands Food and Consumer Product Safety Authority (NVWA), and is responsible for the coordination of suspicions and outbreaks of various notifiable contagious animal diseases and zoonoses at a national level.

Dr. Jeanette de Boer is a medical specialist in Public Health and Infectious disease control. After many years of experience in the regional public health services she started in 2003 at the Dutch training program for medical doctors in communicable diseases. Currently she is heading the faculty of Public Health at the NSPOH. Besides the NSPOH, Jeannette is allied to the Centre for Infections Disease Control at the RIVM as consultant CDC and National Focal point for training in communicable disease control for ECDC, at the unit for Public Health Training. She was involved in training needs assessment

methodology and the conduction of several training modules. Jeannette has been involved as an external expert in several international projects with the aim to build the capacity in Communicable disease control (Twinning, TAIEX and WHO).

Ms. Liesbeth Claassen is a social scientist, interested in how people perceive and respond to personally relevant information. Currently, her research focuses on the perception and communication of environmental (health) risks. She is involved in several projects concerning the development of guidelines and communication materials on controversial and anthropogenic sources of risks, such nuclear accidents, contaminants in soil, food and drinking water and zoonoses.

Ms. Dorothee Roßkamp After working 10 years in emergency healthcare provision, Ms Dorothee Roßkamp pursued a bachelor's degree in European Public Health (2014) and a master's degree in Healthcare Policy, Innovation and Management at Maastricht University (2016). Since then, she has become a senior policy advisor within the National Coordination Centre for Communicable Disease Control (Cib) within the Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM). As such, she is specialized in infectious disease preparedness policy and research, nationally and internationally. Her current tasks include a.o. coordinating the national preparedness platform in the Netherlands and the WHO Collaborating Centre for IHR monitoring & evaluation, as well as supporting IHR implementation in (Dutch) overseas countries and territories.

Ms. Laura van Vossen works as an editor and project assistant at the Centre for Infectious Disease Control at the National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) in the Netherlands. Her main tasks are coordinating and editing updates of guidelines on infectious disease prevention, organizing international workshops and discussion groups on infectious disease prevention and supporting her colleagues in the prevention and control of infectious disease outbreaks. Laura is attending the OHEJP CPD module on Outbreak Preparedness as a co-organizer and will assist her colleagues and the co-facilitators that have a substantive role in the event.

Logistical arrangements

The originally planned 2-day face-to-face meeting included an outbreak simulation game for the delegates to participate in. Due to the restructuring of the event to an online event, this simulation game had to be taken off the agenda, as it would have been too complex for the delegates in the online setting. Therefore, the online event was scheduled for 1.5 days instead.

After the final registration of participating delegates, the local organizers were in frequent email contact with the delegates to answer individual questions and share relevant pre-read materials and information. All email communication with the delegates were pitched with and branded by the Comms team.

The local organizers used the Zoom virtual platform to host the event. Participants received a login code together with joining instructions. In addition, delegates were offered a test session in the week prior to the event to familiarise themselves with the platform. A similar test session was held for the speakers of the event.

The merchandise which was originally sent for the physical event has been used for the virtual event. A small merchandise pack (prep-pack) was sent via mail to each delegate by the local team. This prep-pack included a bag, a notebook, post-it's, a pen, a keychain and an USB stick.

Breakout groups were identified before the event, based on their background (human, animal and environmental health sector) and their geographical locations. A facilitator was originally assigned to each breakout room, however after a similar workshop currently being run at RIVM, showed that there was less open discussion. Consequently, it was decided to only add a facilitator during the simulation of the signalling forum. This approach worked well.

Promotional Campaign

The promotional campaign was managed by the One Health EJP Communications Team and began in December 2019 with a [‘Save the Date’ promotional flyer](#), which communicated the theme of the workshop, dates for the physical workshop (see logistical arrangements), location and target audience. As this was a consortium-only event, this first flyer was disseminated through the internal OHEJP communication channels (monthly education and training activities bulletin) and on the OHEJP website and social media channels when applicable.

A dedicated [web-page](#) was initially created in December 2019 for the physical CPD module which initially described when, where and how much it costs to attend the workshop, along with the save the date flyer, aims of the event and eligibility rules.

In March 2020, the E&T bulletin and OHEJP website was used to communicate the change in organisation from a physical to a virtual event for the OHEJP training events, including this CPD module.

Originally, a full-event flyer was created for the physical event. The full flyer aimed to provide more detailed information about the concept and theme of the workshop, the aims and objectives and target audience. It also provided a link to the application form created by the communications team to attend the workshop, along with the deadline. This was disseminated through the same internal channels described for the save the date flyer.

The applications went through a selection procedure and 25 delegates were selected. However, as the physical event could no longer take place, the previously selected 25 delegates were invited to re-confirm their attendance in October 2020. Of these 25 delegates, 18 delegates had re-registered for the online event.

Before these delegates were re-invited, an updated [full event flyer](#) was created, now with updated information to reflect the new arrangements and updated programme. It also provided a link to a registration form created by the communications team to attend the workshop, along with the deadline. This was disseminated through the E&T bulletin in October and the OHEJP website.

As the speakers were confirmed for the final programme, they were asked to provide short biographies and a headshot photo. These were added to the website page as they were received leading up to the event, and the announcement of these speakers for the CPD module was also shared on social media to increase awareness of the event and traffic to the OHEJP website.

The communications team created branded visual montages from the screenshots and testimonials captured. These montages were used to report and share the successes of this workshop through a [blog post](#), on the [One Health EJP CPD webpage](#). This was shared through the One Health EJP social media channels- [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#), and the following [monthly education and training activities bulletins](#) published in 2020.

Applications and selection procedure

The CPD module on outbreak preparedness was directed at Early Career researchers (<5 years post PhD) from within the One Health EJP consortium network. This is because the workshop was originally designed for 25 delegates. As there are 39 partners making it already competitive without the need for external competition, the organizer would like to allow those from all institutes to have a fair opportunity to apply and attend.

Based on the application form provided by the local course organizers, the Comms team setup a registration form on google forms for delegates. After the application deadline closed for the physical event, 29 application forms were received.

The application forms were managed and evaluated by the local course organizers based on pre-determined criteria (delegates need to be affiliated to a consortium country, delegates should work in a One health relevant function, delegates should be able to participate both event days). There were 11 applications who did not have PhDs (some of these were current PhD students), however many of these worked in relevant positions, or had other relevant experience which would still make them valuable delegates for the course. In total 4 applicants were dismissed based on above mentioned criteria and 25

delegates were invited to register for this free event on the OHEJP website. The registration form facility was setup as tickets on the website by the Comms team.

After re-scheduling to an online event, the previously selected 25 delegates were invited to re-confirm their attendance. Of these 25 delegates, 18 delegates had re-registered for the online event. In addition, the local course organizers offered 5 VIP places to Stakeholders targeted towards early career colleagues at the stakeholder institutions so they were able to participate in the workshop, particularly in the breakout sessions. A VIP place did not need to apply and was a way of involving stakeholders who take a great interest in E&T events.

Delegates

A total of 17 delegates (of which 2 VIPs), finally, participated in the online event. One VIP place taken by EFSA, and a second place was taken by a collaborator at BfR. Below a graphical overview is shown on delegates educational background and affiliated country.

Certificates of Attendance

The Comms Team created a certificate of attendance template, which was distributed by the local course organizers to each individual who successfully attended the online event and returned the distributed evaluation form. Successful attendance was defined as participating at least two (out of three) full sessions of the module. Consequently three of the 18 registered delegates did not receive a certificate of attendance.

Blog Post

Work Package 6 worked closely with the One Health EJP Communications Team to create a blog post to promote the successes of the event, publish photos and testimonials. The published blog post can be found on the One Health EJP website [here](#).

This blog post was promoted in the Education and Training activities monthly bulletins, OHEJP newsletters and through the official OHEJP social media channels.

Testimonials

Permission to publish these testimonials was obtained.

Lead Organiser's Testimonial

Dorothee Rosskamp, National Institute for Public Health and the Environment –
 'Organizing an interactive online module during COVID times was challenging, but highly motivated participants, dedicated speakers and the most supportive Comms team, made it a great experience in the end that exceeded my expectations. Definitely worth repeating.'

Examples of Delegate Testimonials collected

Written permission was obtained from all those who submitted testimonials through their evaluation forms submitted.

Photos

Written permission was obtained from all those in any photographs taken. This was done during the registration application process.

Internal Events Survey information

Name of the activity:	The First One Health EJP Continuing Professional Development Module		
Date:	16 th – 17 th November 2020		
Place:	Online event (Zoom)		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	No
Organisation of a Workshop	Yes	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	Yes	Pitch Event	No
Training	Yes	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	Yes	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	Yes	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	27	Media	0
Industry	1	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers	0		

Annex 1: "Save the Date" Promotional Flyer

 National Institute for Public Health
and the Environment
Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport

Save the Date!

Outbreak Preparedness

The first One Health EJP Continuing
Professional Development Module

Date:
12-13th March 2020

Location:
Utrecht, the Netherlands

Audience:
One Health EJP Consortium Members

Organised by RIVM/Centre for Infectious
Disease Control

Find us on social media

 One Health EJP **#OneHealthEJP**
#OHEJPCpd2020

Annex 2: Full Promotional Flyer

National Institute for Public Health
and the Environment
Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport

A circular inset image showing an aerial view of a city with a prominent church spire, likely Utrecht, under a blue sky with scattered clouds.

One Health EJP
Continuing Professional Development Module
Outbreak Preparedness

Date:
16th & 17th November 2020

Location:
Online module via Zoom

Audience:
Early Career Researchers (< 5 years post PhD)
from across the OHEJP consortium partners with
some experience in a health related field

 ONE Health EJP
#OneHealthEJP #OHEJPCpd2020

Aim of the One Health EJP CPD Module on Outbreak Preparedness:

Outbreaks or events involving new or re-emerging zoonoses can occur anytime and everywhere. The One Health concept recognizes that human health is tightly connected to the health of animals and the environment. Consequently, strengthening the human-veterinary collaboration is essential to prevent, detect and respond to zoonotic threats. Yet, implementation and operationalization of the One Health concept often remains a challenge. In addition, countries differ across Europe (and worldwide) and thus the approaches to One Health issues do also.

Sharing best practices and experiences of One Health approaches stands at the center of this module, providing a learning platform aimed at knowledge integration and strengthening of One Health collaboration across Europe.

This outbreak preparedness module aims to provide:

- an understanding of the basic principles of infectious disease control, as well as monitoring and evaluation;
- a platform to share experiences and lessons learned from past outbreaks;
- an understanding of the Dutch zoonoses response structure, as an example of a One Health approach in prevention and response;
- insight into relevant aspects of risk perception and communication to professionals and the public;
- an interactive learning on risk assessment and response to a zoonotic disease.

The outbreak preparedness module consists of a mixture of online lectures and interactive breakout sessions in working groups. Participants will learn a number of technical skills that they will be able to practice on case studies.

Participants:

Participants which had registered to the One Health EJP CPD module on outbreak preparedness in March 2020.

Registration:

Registration for this event has closed.

Annex 3: Event Programme

National Institute for Public Health
and the Environment
Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport

One Health EJP Continuing Professional Development Module Outbreak Preparedness

Day 1 - 16th November 2020

08:30 - 09:00	Opening of online platform & registration	
09:00 - 09:15	Welcome & opening of the One Health EJP module on outbreak preparedness	
09:15 - 09:30	Course introduction	
09:30 - 10:15	Basic principles of Infectious Disease Control Preparedness, outbreak investigation and response	
10:15 - 11:15	Break out session in working groups: What should be in place in case of an outbreak? <i>(incl. break)</i>	
11:15 - 12:30	Plenary feedback per group (10 minutes per group)	
12:30 - 13:00	Plenary discussion & summary of conclusion	
13:00 - 14:00 Lunchbreak		
14:00 - 15:00	Zoonoses response structure - The example of the Netherlands and lessons learned from past outbreaks	
15:00 - 16:00	Break out session in working groups: Assessment of a signal <i>(incl. break)</i>	
16:00 - 17:00	Simulation exercise of a signal assessment	
17:00 - 17:30	Plenary discussion & summary of conclusion	
17:30 - 18:00 Plenary wrap up and evaluation of day 1		

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One Health EJP Continuing Professional Development Module Outbreak Preparedness

Day 2 - 17th November 2020

08:30 - 09:00

Opening of online platform & registration

09:00 - 09:15

Opening of day 2 and recap day 1

09:15 - 10:00

Risk perception and communication to
professionals and the public

10:00 - 11:00

Break out session in working groups:
How to assess and address information needs and
concerns
(incl. break)

11:00 - 12:15

Plenary feedback per group (10 minutes per group)

12:15 - 12:30

Plenary discussion & summary of conclusion

Jeannette de Boer

Liesbeth Claassen

Kitty Maassen

Hans van den Kerkhof

Ingrid Keur

Dorothee Roßkamp

12:30 - 13:00

Plenary wrap-up, evaluation and closure of the workshop

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